

Your participation in this questionnaire would aid in assessing the current maturity state of Building Information Modeling (BIM) in Kuwait's Architecture/Engineering/Construction (AEC) industry. There are no anticipated risks associated with your participation, yet your input could help in shaping future BIM policies and industry best practices in Kuwait. Your participation is entirely voluntary. You may decline to answer any question or withdraw at any time without consequences. Your responses will be kept confidential and used for research purposes only. The data collected will be securely stored and accessible only to the research team.

By clicking the box below, you acknowledge that you have read and understood the information provided, and you voluntarily agree to participate in this study.

Section 1: General Information

1. Which part of the AEC industry do you represent?
 - a) Architecture/Engineering (AE) Consultant
 - b) Project and Construction Management (PM/CM)
 - c) Contractor
 - d) Subcontractor
 - e) Other (please specify) _____

2. For how many years has your firm been in operation?
 - a) Less than 10 years
 - b) 10 to 20 years
 - c) 21 to 30 years
 - d) 31 to 40 years
 - e) More than 40 years

3. How many employees does your firm have?
 - a) 1-20 employees
 - b) 21-50 employees
 - c) 51-100 employees
 - d) 101-200 employees
 - e) More than 200 employees

4. What is your role in the firm?
 - a) Principal/Partner
 - b) Manager (Project/Construction)
 - c) BIM Specialist
 - d) Architect/Engineer
 - e) Other (please specify) _____

Section 2: BIM Maturity Assessment

Instructions: For each of the following BIM dimensions, please provide two responses:

Agreement Level: Indicate your level of agreement with the statement.

Maturity Level: Select the option that best reflects the current situation in Kuwait's AEC industry, based on the provided descriptions.

BIM Objectives (BO):

5a. There are well-defined BIM objectives, implementation stages and milestones in Kuwait's AEC industry.

- a) Strongly disagree
- b) Disagree
- c) Neither agree nor disagree
- d) Agree
- e) Strongly agree

5b. How would you describe the presence of BIM objectives, stages, and milestones in Kuwait's AEC industry?

- a) None/Undefined (Low)
- b) Well defined (Medium-Low)
- c) Managed and formally monitored (Medium)
- d) Integrated into policies/processes (Medium-High)
- e) Continuously refined according to international best practices (High)

BIM Champions and Drivers (BCD):

6a. There are defined champions and drivers within the Kuwait's AEC industry driving BIM adoption.

- a) Strongly disagree
- b) Disagree
- c) Neither agree nor disagree
- d) Agree
- e) Strongly agree

6b. Describe the leadership and vision regarding BIM adoption in Kuwait's AEC industry.

- a) Varied visions without a guiding strategy (Low)
- b) Common vision but lacks actionable details (Medium-Low)
- c) Clear vision, coupled with detailed action plans and a monitoring system (Medium)
- d) Shared vision, with integrated implementation process (Medium-High)
- e) Internalized vision, proactively aligned with other strategies (High)

Regulatory Framework (RF):

7a. There is an available regulatory framework (contractual laws and types of contracts) covering the digital workflow of BIM projects in Kuwait's AEC industry.

- a) Strongly disagree
- b) Disagree
- c) Neither agree nor disagree
- d) Agree
- e) Strongly agree

7b. Describe the regulatory framework (if any) for BIM projects in Kuwait's AEC industry.

- a) Absent of guidelines/Pre-BIM contracts dependence (Low)
- b) Basic guidelines, requirements are contractually recognized (Medium-Low)
- c) Detailed guidelines, intellectual property/confidentiality/liability management, BIM conflict resolution mechanism. (Medium)
- d) Integrated guidelines, trust-based organization (Medium-High)
- e) Continuously refined, best practices and highest value for all stakeholders. (High)

Noteworthy Publications (NP):

8a. BIM publications of mandates and protocols for Kuwait's AEC industry are available.

- a) Strongly disagree
- b) Disagree
- c) Neither agree nor disagree
- d) Agree
- e) Strongly agree

8b. Describe the availability of publications on BIM mandates/protocols in Kuwait.

- a) Absent (Low)
- b) Availability of basic publications (Medium-Low)
- c) Availability of detailed publications (Medium)
- d) Not only available, but integrated into the process flow (Medium-High)
- e) Continuously assessed and refined to enhance the process flow (High)

Learning and Education (LE):

9a. BIM learning topics are identified and introduced into several education/training programs across Kuwait.

- a) Strongly disagree
- b) Disagree
- c) Neither agree nor disagree
- d) Agree
- e) Strongly agree

9b. Describe the BIM educational framework in Kuwait.

- a) Absent/limited BIM training (Low)
- b) BIM topics are introduced, and BIM learning providers are available (Medium-Low)
- c) BIM learning topics are mapped to roles, and accredited programs are offered (Medium)
- d) BIM learning topics are integrated across educational tiers for all stakeholders. (Medium-High)
- e) BIM learning topics are infused in all programs (High)

Measurements and Benchmarks (MB):

10a. Metrics are available to **measure** BIM competency and project performance in Kuwait.

- a) Strongly disagree
- b) Disagree
- c) Neither agree nor disagree
- d) Agree
- e) Strongly agree

10b. Describe the availability of BIM competency/performance metrics in Kuwait's AEC market.

- a) Absent (Low)
- b) Benchmarks are set (Medium-Low)
- c) Performance against benchmarks is monitored and controlled (Medium)
- d) Performance benchmarks are incorporated into quality management systems. (Medium-High)
- e) Benchmarks are continuously revisited for optimum quality (High)

Standardized Parts (SP):

11a. Kuwait's AEC practices have libraries of standardized BIM objects, items and components.

- a) Strongly disagree
- b) Disagree
- c) Neither agree nor disagree
- d) Agree
- e) Strongly agree

11b. Describe the availability of standardized BIM objects/components in Kuwait's AEC market.

- a) Absent/Undefined (Low)
- b) Available yet follow varied modelling/classification norms and is partially used (Medium-Low)
- c) Standardized and formally used across all project lifecycle phases. (Medium)
- d) Integrated into procurement, project workflows/lifecycle facility operations. (Medium-High)
- e) Continuously optimized and realigned to improve interoperability and connectivity. (High)

Technology Infrastructure (TI):

12a. Kuwait's AEC industry has sufficient software, hardware and network capability to enable high performance of BIM workflows.

- a) Strongly disagree
- b) Disagree
- c) Neither agree nor disagree
- d) Agree
- e) Strongly agree

12b. Describe the technology infrastructure for BIM workflows in Kuwait.

- a) Unregulated and inadequate. (Low)
- b) Unified, standardized within organizations via low-bandwidth connections. (Medium-Low)
- c) Managed, and data are shared across high-bandwidth connections. (Medium)
- d) Strategic, and processes are integrated through seamless real-time sharing mechanism (Medium-High)
- e) Continuously assessed and upgraded with innovative solutions. (High)